

Study of Stability of some Metal-organo Sols. Part II

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The stability of some gel forming metal-organo sols of different grain sizes has been investigated. Applicability of Bhattacharya's equation:

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} \cdot t + \frac{1}{m}$$

during the slow gelation of the sols is discussed. From the values of 'a' in this equation the stability of the sols has been assessed. Sols with average finer particles have been found more stable than those with average coarser ones. The values of the constants 'm' and 'n' in this equation are found greater for univalent gelating ions than those for bivalent ones. These constants, therefore, describe the specific nature of the gelating ions.

The influence of the concentration of the coagulant electrolyte on the coagulation time of sols has been investigated by several workers¹. According to Bhattacharya², the concentration of the coagulant electrolyte 'c' is related to the coagulation time 't' by the relation

$$\frac{1}{c-a} = \frac{n}{m} \cdot t + \frac{1}{m}$$

where 'a', 'm' and 'n' are constants and 'a' has the dimensions of concentration. Ghosh and Gangopadhyay³ have shown that a justification of Bhattacharya's equation can be found on theoretical grounds. In a recent publication Upadhaya and Mushran⁴ have discussed the applicability of Bhattacharya's equation during the slow gelation of some succinate sols. In this communication are recorded our experimental data on the determination of the stability of some gel yielding metal-organo sols in the light of Bhattacharya's equation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sols chosen were those of iron and zirconium adipate. Sols of different grain sizes were prepared by adding different quantities of suitable sodium adipate solution to the metal salt solutions, short of precipitation range and subsequent dialysis. Fresh stock solutions of sodium adipate were prepared by neutralising adipic acid (B. D. H.) solution, with caustic soda (AnalaR) and then making up to the desired concentration. The metal salt solutions employed were of AnalaR grade and the metal contents were estimated by the usual methods.

Iron Adipate Sols.—Three samples of iron adipate sols were prepared by adding to a fixed quantity of the ferric chloride solution, different amounts of sodium adipate solution of suitable concentrations so as to obtain a clear stable sol. The iron content in all the three samples was kept constant by estimating it and diluting the sols with distilled water wherever necessary. The total volume of 500 ml was kept the same in all samples. The three

1. Paine, *Koll. Chem. Belh.*, 1912, 4, 24; Boerink, Thesis, Utrecht, 1961; Paekter, *Kolloid Z.*, 1967, 154, 62; Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1956, 149, 17.
2. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 170, 638.
3. *Ibid.*, 1959, 36, 811.
4. *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, 178, 170.

sols (A_1), (B_1) and (C_1) have the following compositions: Volume of 0.1666M ferrie chloride in each sample was 200.0 ml. Volumes of 0.1666 M sodium adipate in sols (A_1), (B_1) and in (C_1) were respectively 50.0 ml, 60.0 ml. and 70.0 ml. The sols were purified by dialysis for a period of 48 hours at room temperature and preserved in Jena glass bottles at low temperatures to avoid the effect of ageing.

Zirconium Adipate Sols.—Three samples of the zirconium adipate sols were prepared by mixing a fixed quantity of zirconium nitrate and different amounts of sodium adipate, keeping the total volume of 500 ml same in all cases. By estimating the zirconium content in each case, the amount of the same was kept constant by dilution of the sol with distilled water. Sols (A_2), (B_2), and (C_2) had the following compositions: Volume of 0.0833M zirconium nitrate in each sample was 250 ml. Volumes of 0.0417 M sodium adipate in sols (A_2), (B_2) and (C_2) were respectively, 160, 180 and 200 ml. The sols were dialysed for 73 hours at room temperature and preserved in Jena glass bottles at low temperatures.

For determination of the gelling time, fixed amount of the sol was taken in a series of test tubes. In another set of test tubes, were taken different volumes of the standard solution of the gelling electrolyte KCl or K_2SO_4 , diluted with the requisite amount of distilled water to make the total volume same in all cases. The test tubes were thermostated at $32^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ for half an hour and then the sol and the electrolyte were mixed together by mixing back and forth twice and the gelling time was recorded according to Bose and Mushran².

The inverse of the gelling time ' t ' and the concentration in ml were plotted. By extrapolating this graph to $1/t = 0$, we get the concentration of the electrolyte necessary for gelation in infinite time. This value gives ' a ' in the Bhattacharya's equation. The value of ' c ' being known, the value of $(c-a)$ is obtained from which the value of $1/(c-a)$ is then calculated and plotted against time ' t '. Our results with the different sol samples are presented graphically in Figs. 1, 2, 3 ($1/t$ vs. c) and Figs. 4, 5, 6 (t vs. $1/(c-a)$).

FIG. 1. Iron adipate. ' $1/t$ ' Versus ' c '

FIG. 2. Iron adipate. ' $1/t$ ' Versus ' c '

FIG. 3. Zirconium adipate. 't' Versus 'c'

DISCUSSION

Figs. (4-6) indicate that the Bhattacharya's equation agrees well with experimental data. Since 'a' is the concentration of the gelling electrolyte which can solidify the sol in infinite time, it can be taken as a measure to express the stability of a sol. The values of 'a' for the three different sol samples of iron adipate investigated in this paper are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

'a'	Sol A ₁	Sol B ₁	Sol C ₁
Stability value of 'a' when 1/t = 0	0.30	0.20	0.10

It is evident from the above table that the order of the stability is sol A₁ > sol B₁ > sol C₁, i.e., the sol with average finer particles is more stable than with average coarser ones.

From Figs 4-6 representing the plot of 1/(c-a) and 't', the values of m and n have been calculated. The intercept of the straight line on the 1/(c-a) axis, gives the value of

FIG. 4. Iron adipate. 't' Versus 1/c-a

FIG. 5. Iron adipate. 't' Versus 1/c-a

FIG. 6. Iron adipate 't' Versus $1/c-a$

' $1/m$ ', i.e. when $t=0$; from which the value of ' m ' is easily calculated. The slope of the straight line gives the value of ' n/m ' and since the value of ' m ' is known, the value of ' n ' can be calculated. Table II represents the values of ' m ' and ' n ' for the sol A₁ of ironadipate.

TABLE II

Coagulating electrolyte.	Intercept $1/m$.	m	Slope n/m .	' n '
M/30 KCl	1.000	1.000	16.35	16.35
M/300 K ₂ SO ₄	1.576	0.635	23.00	14.80

It is evident from the above table that the values of ' m ' and ' n ' decrease with the increase in valency of gelating ion. These constants therefore describe the specific nature of the gelating ions.

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